

LEVEL OF COMPETENCY OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS UNDER STRENGTHENED TECHNICAL VOCATIONAL EDUCATION PROGRAM (STVEP) AND FACTORS AFFECTING IT: A BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the competency levels of Senior High School students enrolled in the Strengthened Technical-Vocational Education Program (STVEP) at the Isabela School of Fisheries for the academic year 2024-2025. The students specialized in Aquaculture, Carpentry, Food Processing, and Organic Agriculture Production. The study aimed to assess students' perceived competencies in these specializations and identify factors influencing their competencies. The research involved a descriptive method, using questionnaires administered to 126 students and their teachers. The study focused on student-related factors, teacher-related factors, administrative support, parent support, and the availability of facilities and equipment. The results indicate varying levels of competency, with students in Aquaculture and Organic Agriculture Production performing more proficiently compared to those in Carpentry and Food Processing. Factors such as student interest, study habits, teacher personality, teaching strategies, instructional materials, and administrative support significantly impacted student competencies. The study found significant differences in perceptions between students and teachers, particularly in Aquaculture, Carpentry, and Organic Agriculture. Recommendations include prioritizing teacher training, improving instructional materials, enhancing school facilities, and fostering stronger parental support. This study underscores the importance of these factors in achieving competency in technical-vocational education and suggests areas for future improvements in curriculum planning and teacher development.

Keywords: *Technical-Vocational Education, Competency Assessment, Senior High School, Aquaculture, Carpentry, Teacher Training*

INTRODUCTION

Technical and vocational education is recognized as the “master key to sustainable development” globally. In line with the trust of the government to bring back technical-vocational education in public and private secondary schools and to create a better link between schools and industries, the Department of Education is continuously enhancing the Competency-Based Curriculum of the Strengthened Technical and Vocational Education Program (STVEP).

Along with the enrichment of the curriculum (STVEP), they also identified appropriate competencies (Basic, Common, and Core) which are crucial in the development of integrated and holistic learning outcomes. In turn, this will serve as basis for the development of appropriate instructional materials, preparation of learning and laboratory activities, adaptation of teaching-learning activities and development of skills leading to competency assessment.

The Technical-Vocational Education Task Force Office, in its efforts to provide over-all guidance and policy direction in the efficient and effective implementation of STVEP. Tech-Voc teachers/facilitators who comprise the Tech-Voc Task force for the development of technical key competencies play a vital role in enhancing the learner’s knowledge, skills and attitudes in their field of specialization.

The goal of TECH-VOC schools is to make technical vocational offerings relevant to the needs of learners, the community and industries to absorb them. During the celebration of the 48th Philippine Business Conference and Expo Philippine Chamber of Commerce and Industries, Vice President Sarah Duterte, expressed hopes that the business sector would provide more job opportunities for Grade 12 graduates. Duterte said this is crucial not only for the lives of young graduates but also for nation-building (Lemit, 2022). The Department of labor and employment assumes that there are plenty of local jobs in the country. It has logged an estimated 200,000 vacancies by employees on the enhanced phil.jobnet, the government online job searches, therefore to produce learners who are equipped with highly competent skills that can find engagement in local and international labor markets the student must undergo National Assessment to acquire the National Certificate (NC) in their field of specialization to become eligible in the qualification.(STVEP, 2007)

To evaluate the assessment readiness of the learners prior to National Assessment, the teacher conducts pre-assessment activity and institutional assessment. There are three parts of assessment period namely, the written test, oral questioning and performance test based on their qualification (Basic competencies, Common competencies and Core competencies). The mastery of all competencies is a must to pass the National Assessment. In partnership with TESDA, R.A No.7796 known as Republic Act of 1994 created the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority

to provide relevant, accessible high quality and efficient technical education and skills development in support of development of higher quality Filipino, middle- level manpower responsive to and in accordance with Philippine development and Priorities.

TESDA plays a vital role in assessing the learner's skills as consultants/experts, writers and evaluators. Senior High school learners who may want to pursue middle level skills development after finishing Technical Vocational Livelihood Track may inquire at their local TESDA offices for the course's offerings in their locality. After earning National Certificate (NC) level I & II, they may also apply higher level of National Certificate if they want it.

The School of Fisheries in Isabela sees to it that students pass the National Assessment or National Certification. An assessor is invited to evaluate the skills of the students depending on their specialization. It is observed that yearly, 100% of the students passed the NC assessment and it is challenging because the school need to maintain its standing of 100% passing rate. It is for this reason that the school has to plan and enhance the readiness of every student.

Hence, the researcher decided to venture into this study to find out how students are prepared for the National Certificate (NC) assessment in their field of specialization, particularly in Aquaculture, Carpentry, Food Processing and Organic Agriculture by using the learning competencies and the different factors affecting these different competencies.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the level of competence of Senior High School students in their respective specialization under the Strengthen Technical –Vocational Education Program for school year 2024-2025, (Aquaculture NCII, Carpentry NC II, Food Processing NC II and Organic Agriculture Production NCII)

Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions.

1. How competent are the students in their respective specializations as perceived by them and their teachers?
2. Is there a significant difference in the perception of students and teachers on the competencies of the students in their respective specializations?
3. What are the factors affecting the competencies of the students in their specialization in terms of:
 - a. Student- Related
 - b. Teacher- Related
 - c. Administrative Support
 - d. Parent Support
 - e. Facilities and Equipment
4. Is there a significant difference in the factors affecting the competencies of students when grouped according to specialization?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the competencies of the students and the identified factors?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive method was used in this study. According to Calderon and Gonzales (2023) the said method is a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, such as practices, beliefs, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships, and then making adequate and accurate interpretations. This is the most appropriate method to be used by the researcher for her to gather, analyze, and interpret her data on the competencies and factors affecting Senior High School in their field of specialization.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at the Isabela School of Fisheries involving the Senior High School students in the following field of specialization: Aquaculture, Carpentry, Food processing, and Organic Agriculture Production during the S.Y. 2024-2025.

The Isabela School of Fisheries is one of the secondary schools implementing the Strengthened Technical-Vocational Education Program (STVEP) and is in the coastal area of Isabela. Technical Vocational schools are designed to equip students with relevant knowledge, skills, and attitudes that will lead them to become competent in their field of specialization and prepare students for higher education, the world of work, or entrepreneurship.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this study are the 126 Senior High School students under SPTVEP for the S.Y. 2024-2025 of the Isabela School of Fisheries and their teachers. Below shows the breakdown of Senior High School students per specialization. The number of respondents comprises the total population of STVE students.

Table 1
Respondents of the Study

Specialization	Number of Students	Teachers
Aquaculture	19	1
Carpentry	38	1
Food Processing	33	1
Organic Agriculture Production	36	1
Total	126	4

Data Gathering Procedure

A letter requesting permission to conduct the study was forwarded to the Schools Division Superintendent of Isabela. After approval was granted, the researcher coordinated with the principals and/or school heads of the Isabela Schools of Fisheries. The researcher also coordinated with the specialization teachers at Senior High School students to float the approved questionnaire. The objectives of the study were explained to the respondents. The researcher explained to the students how to complete the questionnaire. After the completion of the questionnaire, these were collected, grouped, collated and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were applied in this study to analyze the gathered data.

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution. These were used to determine the level of competencies of the students in the TVL track.

Weighted Average Mean (WAM). This was applied to determine the factors affecting the level of competence of the students.

F-test. This was used to determine if there is significant difference in the level of competence of students according to specialization.

The Pearson-r test. It was employed to find out the significant relationship between the level of competence of Senior High School and the identified factors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. How competent are the students in their respective specialization as perceived by them and their teachers?

Table 2
Students' Competencies in Aquaculture as Perceived by
Them and their Teachers

Aquaculture Competencies	Students		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
BASIC COMPETENCIES				
1. Participate in Workplace communication	3.86	Advance	3.00	Competent
2. Work in team environment	3.80	Advance	3.00	Competent
3. Practice career professionalism	3.43	Advance	3.00	Competent

4. Practice occupational health and safety procedures	3.80	Advance	3.00	Competent
Total	3.72	Advance	3.00	Competent
Common Competencies				
1. Can control hazards and risk	3.41	Advance	3.00	Competent
2. Can maintain occupation health and safety awareness	3.20	Advance	3.00	Competent
Total	3.30	Advance	3.00	Competent
Core Competencies				
Prepare for Tools and Simple Equipment	4.21	Expert	3.00	Competent
Change Water of Aquaculture Facility	3.79	Advance	3.00	Competent
Identify mortalities	3.41	Advance	3.00	Competent
Prepare and Maintain Aquaculture Facilities (Pm)	3.86	Advance	3.00	Competent
Prepare and Maintain Fish Nurseries (Ph)	3.70	Advance	3.00	Competent
Store Feeds and analyze feeding	3.70	Advance	3.00	Competent
Identify and Monitor Water Quality	3.87	Advance	3.00	Competent
Diagnose Fish Health Management	3.70	Advance	3.00	Competent
Harvest and Post-Harvest Handling	3.97	Advance	3.00	Competent
Prepare Grow-Out Facilities	3.92	Advance	3.00	Competent
Install Pens and Cages	3.70	Advance	3.00	Competent
Clean and disinfect Tanks	4.05	Advance	3.00	Competent
Stock Fingerlings	3.75	Advance	3.00	Competent
Stock Sampling	3.85	Advance	3.00	Competent
Perform Feeding Operations	3.80	Advance	3.00	Competent
Maintain Good Water Quality	3.60	Advance	3.00	Competent
Perform Common Disease Diagnosis and Treatment	3.72	Advance	3.00	Competent
Harvest and post-harvest handling	3.91	Advance	3.00	Competent
Total	3.80	Advance	3.00	Competent
Total Mean	3.59	Advance	3.00	Competent

The level of competence of the aquaculture students is shown in Table 2. The data reveals that in terms of basic competencies, the students perceive themselves to have **advanced** skills in participating in workplace communication, working in a team environment, practicing career professionalism, and occupational health and safety procedures. As to core competencies, they consider themselves **expert** in preparing tools and simple equipment and have advanced competence in cleaning and disinfecting tanks, harvest and post-harvest handling, preparing grow-out facilities, identifying and monitoring water quality and preparing and maintaining aquaculture facilities, among others. On the average, the students perceive themselves to have passed and mastered the competencies in aquaculture as shown in the mean of 3.80. When asked why they consider themselves to have advanced skill, they replied, *“halos alam na po namin ang ginagawa namin kasi napag aralan na namin ang mga ito noong nasa Junior high school kami. Some students added, “ memoryado napo namin ang mga ginagamit namin sa shop”*. This attests that students can already memorize the equipment because it is one

9. Interpret Technical Drawings and Plan	2.51	Developing	2.57	Developing
10. Apply Freehand Sketching	2.30	Developing	2.54	Developing
11. Identify Hazards and Risks	3.08	Competent	2.55	Developing
12. Control Hazards and Risks	2.50	Developing	2.53	Developing
13. Maintain Occupational Health and Safety Awareness	2.85	Competent	2.54	Developing
Total	2.80	Competent	2.59	Developing
Core Competencies				
1. Prepare Tools, Equipment and Materials for Staking Out Building Lines	3.23	Competent	3.32	Competent
2. Stake Out and Set Batter Boards	2.57	Developing	2.94	Competent
3. Fix Building Lines	3.00	Competent	2.96	Competent
4. Fabricate Formworks (Fw)	3.24	Competent	3.00	Competent
5. Lay-Out and Cut to Dimension of Form Sheathing and Stiffeners	2.55	Developing	2.70	Competent
6. Assemble Form Panels	2.17	Developing	2.70	Competent
7. Prepare Tools and Materials for Installing Formworks Components/Form Panels	2.97	Competent	3.30	Competent
8. Lay-Out/Assemble Scaffolds and Braces	2.77	Competent	2.65	Competent
9. Set/Fix Formworks Components/Form Panels	2.68	Competent	2.72	Competent
Total	2.79	Competent	2.92	Competent
Total Mean	2.68	Competent	2.61	Competent

Table 3 presents the level of competence of the students in carpentry. Findings show that students have advanced basic competencies in carpentry, like leading workplace communication and leading small teams, developing and practicing negotiation skills, solving problems related to work activities, and using relevant technologies. In terms of the common competencies, the students consider themselves advanced in identifying materials and tools for a task and competent in checking the condition of tools and equipment, performing basic preventive maintenance, selecting measuring instruments, carrying out measurements and calculations, analyzing signs, symbols, and data, and identifying hazards and risks. However, they assessed themselves to be on the developing stage in requesting appropriate materials and tools, interpreting technical drawings and planning, applying freehand sketching, and controlling hazards and risks. As to the core competencies, the students assessed themselves as competent in preparing tools, equipment, and materials for taking out building lines, fixing building lines, fabricating formworks (Fw), preparing tools and materials for installing formworks components/form panels, laying out/assembling scaffolds and braces, and setting/fixing formworks components/form panels. They are still **developing** in staking out and setting batter boards, laying out and cutting to dimensions of form sheathing and Stiffeners, and assembling form panels.

Students are good with the materials and tools needed in their shop. This proves that the students recognize their abilities in the materials they use in their field of specialization. When asked why they knew and could identify all the materials needed,

majority of them replied that these are the daily materials used in applying the different competencies ahead. Though students are good at identifying the materials they used, they have difficulty assessing what the usage of these materials are and how to keep or inspect it.

Aside from that, they are also being challenged in measurements and calculations and safety and protection. The students in carpentry have difficulties in mathematical procedures and assessing health awareness. Students at times are complaining especially if they will compute inches to centimeters or vice versa. They still need calculators to measure things. Aside from mathematical problems, they also feel uncomfortable working if they use safety gears needed while they are working such as protective masks, safety glasses, and gloves.

In a study made by Sehsah, et.al. (2020), they found that the main reasons for non-use are discomfort, lack of knowledge on how to use it and poor fit, being uncomfortable, not knowing their importance or proper use, poor fit, resultant heat stress and unavailability of materials. In a study conducted by Wildah, et.al.(2024), it revealed that the errors experienced by students in solving mathematical problems on SPLTV material were the method used to match what was taught, and mistakes in calculations. They also found that the factors that caused students' errors were lack of accuracy, misunderstanding of concepts, or needing to be more fixated on example questions.

The teachers assessed the students as **competent** in the basic and core competencies and **developing** in the common competencies.

Table 4
Students' Competencies in Food Processing as Assessed by Them and their Teachers

Food Processing Competencies	Students		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
Basic Competencies				
1. Select Tools, Equipment, Utensils and Instruments	2.63	Competent	3.46	Advance
2. Perform Estimation and Basic Calculation	2.44	Developing	3.26	Competent
3. Interpret Plans and Drawings (Id)	2.26	Developing	2.89	Competent
4. Apply Food Safety and Sanitation (Os)	2.63	Competent	2.93	Competent
Total	2.49	Developing	3.13	Competent
Common Competencies				
1. Implement Sampling Procedures (Sa)	2.22	Developing	2.44	Developing
2. Inspect And Sort Raw Materials and Product	2.69	Competent	2.89	Competent
3. Dispense Non-Bulk Ingredients (Nb)	2.61	Competent	2.55	Developing
4. Prepare Raw and Packaging Materials And Supplies For Processing (Pr)	2.65	Competent	2.65	Competent
5. Operate Equipment (Eo)	2.51	Developing	2.82	Competent
6. Clean And Sanitize Equipment and Processing/Packaging Area (Cs)	2.86	Competent	3.03	Competent

7. Load And Unload Raw Materials, Products and Supplies (Ld)	2.37	Developing	2.46	Developing
Total	2.55	Developing	2.69	Competent
Core Competencies				
1. Process Food by Salting, Curing and Smoking	2.88-	Competent	2.86	Competent
2. Process Foods by Fermentation and Pickling (Fr)	2.5	Developing	2.44	Developing
3. Process Food by Sugar Concentration (Sc)	2.68	Competent	2.32	Developing
4. Package Finished/Processed Food Products (Pk)	2.77	Competent	2.35	Developing
5. Processed Fish by Vacuum or Ordinary Ply-Packing (Vp)	2.57	Developing	2.36	Developing
6. Package Processed Fish by Bottling (Bo)	2.44	Developing	2.39	Developing
7. Packaged Processed Fish by Canning (Cn)	2.61	Competent	2.30	Developing
Total	2.63	Competent	2.43	Developing
Total	2.57	Developing	2.69	Competent

Table 4 presents the competencies of students in Food Processing. The students assessed themselves as **competent** in the basic competencies like performing estimation and basic calculation, interpreting plans and drawings (Id), and applying food safety and sanitation (Os). In terms of the common competencies, they are in the **developing** stage in implementing sampling procedures, dispensing non-bulk ingredients, and loading and unloading raw materials, products, and supplies, and are **competent** in inspecting and sorting raw materials and products, preparing raw and packaging materials and supplies for processing, and operating equipment. As to core competencies, they consider themselves **competent** in processing food by salting, curing, and smoking, processing food by sugar concentration, packaging finished/processed food products, and packaging processed fish by canning. They are in the **developing** stage in processed foods by fermentation and pickling, processing fish by vacuum or ordinary poly-packing, and packaging processed fish by bottling.

The teachers assessed their students to be competent in the basic and common competencies, but developing in the core competencies.

In a study by Joardder and Masud (2019), most of the mistakes in food processing are associated with a lack of attention, guidelines, as well as knowledge relating to the food preservation system. Diverse factors contribute to the overall challenges in food preservation systems, such as a lack of facilities, the incorporation of technology, technical support, and the necessary knowledge are key factors that severely reduce the performance system.

Moreover, the study by Zamora-Sereguine (2020) found a significant relationship between the academic performance of the TVE students and the support learning facilities, and between the academic performance of the TVE students and the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in learning.

Table 5
Competence of Organic Agriculture Students as Assessed by Them and their Teachers

Competencies	Students		Teachers	
	Mean	Verbal Description	Mean	Verbal Description
Basic Competencies				
1. Participate in Workplace Communication	2.72	Competent	3.04	Competent
2. Work In Team Environment	2.90	Competent	3.25	Competent
3. Practice Career Professionalism	2.93	Competent	3.26	Competent
4. Practice Occupational Health and Safety Procedures	3.06	Competent	2.95	Competent
Total	2.90	Competent	3.12	Competent
Common Competencies				
1. Apply Safety Measures in Farm Operations	3.42	Advance	2.97	Competent
2. Use Farm Tools and Equipment	3.25	Competent	3.20	Competent
3. Perform Estimation and Basic Calculation	2.86	Competent	2.96	Competent
4. Develop and Update Industry Knowledge	2.86	Competent	2.95	Competent
5. Perform Record Keeping	3.02	Competent	2.97	Competent
Total	3.08	Competent	3.01	Competent
Core Competencies				
Lesson 1: Raising Organic Chicken	2.91	Competent	2.91	Competent
Lesson 2: Produce Organic Vegetables	2.99	Competent	3.12	Competent
Lesson 3: Produce Organic Fertilizer	2.99	Competent	3.13	Competent
Total	2.96	Competent	3.05	Competent
WAM	2.98	Competent	3.06	Competent

Table 5 shows the students' and teachers' assessment of the competencies of students in Organic Agriculture. The data reveal that both the students and teachers assess the students as **competent** in the basic, common, and core competencies. Students' competence in applying safety measures and farm operations is considered **advanced**, as perceived by the students.

Based on the data gathered, the students do not have problems in Organic Agriculture. According to them, they are not hard up because they are used to doing farm-related activities when they help their parents in the farm. They added that often than not, they are obliged to help in the family business.

The findings negate the findings of Lavadia, et.al. (2021) that majority of the freshmen have a negative attitude towards the agriculture program. As a student's in-depth knowledge of the agriculture field increases, their perception and idea of the program is also positively influenced. Contrary to the popular belief that agriculture is a

male-dominated field, most of the students enrolled in the course are female (63%). Recommendations to make Agriculture more attractive to youth through information dissemination (i.e. ICT-based modalities, infomercials) and interactive campaigns will promote the discipline to increase the interest of the youth and subsequently, the popularity of the program. In addition, TESDA Deputy Director General Aniceto Bertiz III, in a recent TV interview, said that in line with the administration's goal towards food security, they have prioritized the technical vocational training of our Filipino farmers, especially among young people in the urban and rural areas. He added that from January to October 12 this year, the total number of individuals who enrolled in agriculture-related tech-voc courses reached 137,206, of which 135,571 have already graduated. For the first three quarters of 2022, the agriculture, forestry, and fishery sector accounted for almost 18 percent of the total number of tech-voc graduates.(TESDA, 2022)

Table 6
Summary of the TVL Students' Competencies as Assessed by Them and their Teachers

TVL Track	Students		Teachers	
	Mean	Verbal Description	Mean	Verbal Description
Aquaculture	3.59	Advance	3.00	Competent
Carpentry	2.68	Competent	2.61	Competent
Food processing	2.57	Developing	2.69	Competent
Organic Agriculture	2.98	Competent	3.06	Competent

Table 5 displays the summary of the competence of TVL students as assessed by them and their teachers. The aquaculture students assess themselves to be in the advanced stage, while their teachers assessed them as competent. Students in carpentry and organic agriculture consider themselves **competent**, which is affirmed by their teachers' assessment. The food processing students rated themselves to be in the developing stage while their teachers rated them though their teachers rated them as competent.

Based on the interview conducted among students in aquaculture, their advanced competencies are attributed to the fact that they live with fishermen. As for the students in food processing, they mentioned that materials and equipment are needed for them to meet their competencies, especially in packaging the products. The lack of materials, according to them, affects the students' ability to develop their skills and meet industry standards.

In the study of Torres and Andicoy (2024), findings reveal that the lack of tools and equipment is caused by the lower priority of the school. The absence of the tools and equipment affects the psychological drive of the student participants such as fading interest and motivation to do practical applications in the field. This resulted in their views of tools and equipment incompetence. Despite this problem, the resourcefulness and initiatives of the TVL teacher paralleled the absence of the new tools and equipment.

Thus, the study suggests that the school should prioritize purchasing tools and equipment for students and teachers to learn and be competent in their field.

2. Is there a significant difference in the perception of students and teachers in the competencies of students?

Table 7
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in The Perception of Students and Teachers on the Competencies of the Students

Competencies of students according to their specialization as perceived by them and their teachers.	Mean		P-value	Analysis	Remarks
	Teachers	Students			
Aquaculture	3.04	3.73	0.0003	P < 0.05	Significant
Carpentry	2.57	2.93	0.0050	P < 0.05	Significant
Food Processing	2.65	2.58	0.3048	P > 0.05	Not Significant
Organic Agriculture Production	3.27	3.06	0.0432	P < 0.05	Significant

Table 7 presents the results of the test of significant differences in the perception of students and teachers in the competencies of the students.

The results show that the P- values of t are less than 0.05 except for food processing. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perception of students and teachers in the competencies of the students specializing on Aquaculture, Carpentry, and Organic Agriculture Production. It implies that the students and teachers differ in their assessment of the competencies of the students along the said three areas of specialization. As indicated by the mean values, the students specializing on Aquaculture, and Carpentry have better assessment of their competencies than their teachers, while the teachers of Organic Agriculture Production have better assessment of their students' competencies than the students' assessment.

However, there is no significant difference in the perception of students and teachers on the competencies of the students majoring in Food Processing. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 significance level. It implies that the teachers and students have similar perceptions of the students' competencies in Food Processing.

3. What are the factors affecting the competencies of the students in their specialization ?

Table 8
Factors Affecting the Competencies of the Students in Aquaculture

Factors	Mean	Qualitative Description
I. Student Factors		
A. Interest		
1. I prepare myself for the specialization subject.	4.63	Always
2. I actively participate during the discussion by answering self-check.	4.32	Always
3. I listen attentively to the lecture of my specialization teacher.	4.58	Always
4. I classify things/lessons I do not understand.	4.16	Often
5. I perform the task given by the teacher by following the standard specification	4.47	Always
Total Mean	4.43	Always
I. Student Factors		
B. Habits		
1. I review my lesson and prepare for pre-test and post-test.	4.42	Always
2. I spend vacant time doing assignments or studying my lesson.	3.95	Often
3. I prefer finishing my study and homework first before using the internet/watching TV.	4.21	Always
4. I exert more effort when my teacher gives me a performance task.	4.68	Always
5. I study harder to improve my performance when I get few performances grade.	4.37	Always
Total Mean	4.33	Always
II. Teacher/School Factors		
A. Teaching Personality		
1. My teacher is student friendly.	4.26	Always
2. My teacher has appealing personality with good sense of humor.	4.42	Always
3. My teacher is smart and fair in making decisions.	4.42	Always
4. My teacher always gives praise.	4.47	Always
5. My teacher is open to suggestions and opinions.	4.63	Always
Total Mean	4.44	Always

B. Teaching Strategy		
1. My teacher explains the objectives of the lesson clearly at the very beginning.	4.74	Always
2. My teacher has mastery of the subject matter	4.47	Always
3. My teacher is a National Certificate and Trainers Methodology holder.	4.42	Always
4. My teacher is updated with present competencies needed.	4.74	Always
5. My teacher uses various strategies and techniques in presenting the lessons.	4.74	Always
Total Mean	4.62	Always

Factors	Mean	Qualitative Description
I. Student Factors		
C. Study Habits		
1. I review my lesson and prepare for pre-test and post-test.	4.42	Always
2. I spend vacant time doing assignments or studying my lesson.	3.95	Often
3. I prefer finishing my study and homework first before using the internet/watching TV.	4.21	Always
4. I exert more effort when my teacher gives me a performance task.	4.68	Always
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3. My teacher is a National Certificate and Trainers Methodology holder.	4.42	Always
4. My teacher is updated with present competencies needed.	4.74	Always
5. My teacher uses various strategies and techniques in presenting the lessons.	4.74	Always
Total Mean	4.62	Always
2. Instructional Materials		
1. My teacher uses power point presentation to deliver his/her lesson.	3.79	Often
2. My teacher uses local materials to execute the performance task.	4.42	Always
3. Total Mean	4.10	Often
4. Facilities and Equipment		
5. Learning facilities provided (library, specialization laboratory, computer laboratory & checkboard) are used by students.	4.32	Always
6. Learning facilities in performing the performance task in their field of specialization are used.	4.68	Always
7. The specialization laboratory of lecture area is standard and washable (classroom size, lighting, air conditioning, table & chair)	4.42	Always
Total Mean	4.47	Always
D. Administrative Support		
1. Address issues promptly and effectively	4.37	Always
2. Accepts responsibility to facilitate programs	4.53	Always
3. Fairly allocates funding support programs	4.53	Always
4. Effectively support students generating projects	4.42	Always
5. Effectively supports and facilitates students advising and progress	5.00	Always
6. Facilitates student activities to enhance development	4.74	Always
Total Mean	4.46	Always
F. Parent Factor		
1. Parents provide all their materials needed to perform well in their field of specialization.	4.42	Always
2. Has adequate parental support	4.30	
3. Consistently monitor their children's progress	4.37	Always
4. Check outputs of their children	4.37	Always
5. Motivates their children in times of overlapping activities	4.42	Always

Total Mean	4.38	Always
Average WM	4.40	Always

Table 8 presents the factors affecting the aquaculture competencies of the TVL students. It shows that the student factors like interest (4.43) and study habits (4.33) always affect the competence of students. The teacher-related factors like teacher personality (4.44) and teaching strategy (4.62) always affect the students' competence while the teacher's instructional materials (4.10) often affect the students' competence. School factors such as administrative factor (4.46) and facilities and equipment (4.47) always affect students' competence

Based on the result, it shows that all the identified factors always influence the competence of students except for the teacher's instructional materials. This shows that textbooks, lectures, readings, multimedia components, and other resources used by the teachers often affect the competencies of the aquaculture students.

Anthony and Andala (2023), in their study reveal that instructional materials have a great influence on improving learners/students' capacity for understanding and increasing their academic performance and achievement. It was noted that instructional materials are essential to improving quality education. In addition, the instructional materials are the primary need in developing the skills of all the learners in the SHS-TVL schools undertaking the successful conduct of all the activities inside the classroom. Students learning progress is hindered by the insufficiency of instructional resources according to Barrera (2022).

Table 9
Factors Affecting the Competencies of the Students in Carpentry

I. Student Related Factors	Mean	Qualitative Description
A. Interest		
1. I prepare myself for the specialization subject.	4.16	Often
2. I actively participate during the discussion by answering self-check.	4.16	Often
3. I listen attentively to the lecture of my specialization teacher.	4.11	Often
4. I classify things/lessons I do not understand.	3.76	Often
5. I perform the task given by the teacher by following the standard specification	4.08	Often
Total Mean	4.05	Often
B. Study Habits		

1. I review my lesson and prepare for pre-test and post-test.	3.66	Often
2. I spend vacant time doing assignments or studying my lesson.	3.16	Sometimes
3. I prefer finishing my study and homework first before using the internet/watching TV.	3.39	Sometimes
4. I exert more effort when my teacher gives me a performance task.	3.76	Often
5. I study harder to improve my performance when I get few performances grade.	3.66	Often
Total Mean	3.52	Often

II. Teachers/School Related Factors	Mean	Qualitative Description
A. Teaching Personality		
1. 1. My teacher is student friendly.	4.29	Always
2. 2. My teacher has appealing personality with good sense of humor.	4.26	Always
3. 3. My teacher is smart and fair in making decisions.	4.39	Always
4. 4. My teacher always gives praise.	4.34	Always
5. 5. My teacher is open to suggestions and opinions.	4.21	Always
Total Mean	4.30	Always
B. Teaching Strategy		
1. 1. My teacher explains the objectives of the lesson clearly at the very beginning.	4.24	Always
2. 2. My teacher has mastery of the subject matter	4.26	Always
3. 3. My teacher is a National Certificate and Trainers Methodology holder.	4.47	Always
4. 4. My teacher is updated with present competencies needed.	4.39	Always
5. 5. My teacher uses various strategies and techniques in presenting the lessons.	4.32	Always
Total Mean	4.34	Always
C. Instructional Materials		

1. My teacher uses power point presentation to deliver his/her lesson.	3.79	Often
2. My teacher uses local materials to execute the performance task.	4.11	Often
Total Mean	3.95	Often
D. Facilities and Equipment		
1. Learning facilities provided (library, specialization laboratory, computer laboratory & checkboard) are used by students.	3.92	Often
2. Learning facilities in performing the performance task in their field of specialization are used.	4.16	Often
3. The specialization laboratory of lecture area is standard and washable (classroom size, lighting, air conditioning, table & chair)	4.03	Often
Total Mean	4.04	Often

III. Administrative Support	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Address issues promptly and effectively	3.74	Often
2. Accepts responsibility to facilitate programs	3.84	Often
3. Fairly allocates funding support programs	3.92	Often
4. Effectively support students generating projects	4.11	Often
5. Effectively supports and facilitates students advising and progress	4.00	Often
6. Facilitates student activities to enhance development	3.92	Often
Total Mean	3.92	Often
IV. Parent Factor		
1. Parents provide all their materials needed to perform well in their field of specialization.	4.11	Often
2. Has adequate parental support	3.90	Often
3. Consistently monitor their children's progress	3.89	Often
4. Check outputs of their children	4.00	Often
5. Motivates their children in times of overlapping activities	3.92	Often
Total Mean	3.96	Often

Average WM	4.01	Often
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The factors affecting the competencies of carpentry students are presented in Table 9. Data shows that the student-related factors particularly the interest and study habits of students **often** affect their competence level. Teacher's personality and teaching strategy **always** affect their competence level. The instructional materials, administrative support factor and parent factor often influence the students' mastery of the competencies.

Findings reveal that of all the factors, it is the teachers' personality and teaching strategy that strongly influences the students' mastery of the competencies. It was presented that all the factors often affect the competencies while the teacher's personality and their strategy always affect the student's competencies.

According to Maazouzi (2019), teaching and learning process can be influenced by the teacher's personality and mentality either positively or negatively. If the teacher has positive traits like being passionate, patient, cooperative, and authoritative, he/she is able to win his students' satisfaction. The teacher is both an instructor and a learner. However, the learners in the classroom environment behave in response to the teacher method. The way he behaves, explains the lesson and interacts with the students during a course of study has a great impact on their success and achievement. Moreover, constructive teacher-student relationships have a large and positive impact on students' academic results. The best teachers are those who have good personality and good behavior towards their students and could combine between two subjects: teaching and educating.

Table 10
Factors Affecting the Competencies of the Students in Food Processing

I. Student Related Factors	Mean	Qualitative Description
A. Interest		
1. I prepare myself for the specialization subject.	3.70	Often
2. I actively participate during the discussion by answering self-check.	3.55	Often
3. I listen attentively to the lecture of my specialization teacher.	4.27	Always
4. I classify things/lessons I do not understand.	3.58	Often
5. I perform the task given by the teacher by following the standard specification	4.15	Often
Total Mean	3.85	Often
I. Student Related Factors	Mean	Qualitative Description

B. Study Habits		
1. I review my lesson and prepare for pre-test and post-test.	3.18	Sometimes
2. I spend vacant time doing assignments or studying my lesson.	3.12	Sometimes
3. I prefer finishing my study and homework first before using the internet/watching TV.	3.15	Sometimes
4. I exert more effort when my teacher gives me a performance task.	3.70	Often
5. I study harder to improve my performance when I get few performances grade.	3.85	Often
Total Mean	3.40	Often
II. Teachers – Related Factors		
A. Teaching Personality		
1. My teacher is student friendly.	4.42	Always
2. My teacher has appealing personality with good sense of humor.	4.36	Always
3. My teacher is smart and fair in making decisions.	4.48	Always
4. My teacher always gives praise.	4.03	Often
5. 5. My teacher is open to suggestions and opinions.	4.36	Always
Total Mean	4.33	Often
B. Teaching Strategy	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. 1. My teacher explains the objectives of the lesson clearly at the very beginning.	4.55	Always
2. 2. My teacher has mastery of the subject matter	4.48	Always
3. 3. My teacher is a National Certificate and Trainers Methodology holder.	4.30	Always
4. 4. My teacher is updated with present competencies needed.	4.36	Always
5. 5. My teacher uses various strategies and techniques in presenting the lessons.	4.36	Always
Total Mean	4.41	Always
C. Instructional Materials		
1. My teacher uses power point presentation to deliver his/her lesson.	3.12	Sometimes

2. My teacher uses local materials to execute the performance task.	4.15	Often
Total Mean	3.64	Often
D. Facilities and Equipment		
1. Learning facilities provided (library, specialization laboratory, computer laboratory & checkboard) are used by students.	4.09	Often
2. Learning facilities in performing the performance task in their field of specialization are used.	4.18	Often
3. The specialization laboratory of lecture area is standard and washable (classroom size, lighting, air conditioning, table & chair)	4.36	Always
Total Mean	4.21	Always
III. Administrative Support Factor		
1. Address issues promptly and effectively	3.85	Often
2. Accepts responsibility to facilitate programs	3.88	Often
3. Fairly allocates funding support programs	4.00	Often
4. Effectively support students generating projects	3.91	Often
5. Effectively supports and facilitates students advising and progress	4.00	Often
6. Facilitates student activities to enhance development	4.03	Often
Total Mean	3.95	Often

IV. Parent Factor	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Parents provide all their materials needed to perform well in their field of specialization.	4.06	Often
2. Has adequate parental support	3.45	
3. Consistently monitor their children's progress	3.61	Often
4. Check outputs of their children	3.48	Often
5. Motivates their children in times of overlapping activities	3.64	Often
Total Mean	3.65	Often
WAM	3.93	Often

Table 10 presents the factors affecting the competencies of the students in food processing. It discloses that students' interest and study habits, administrative factor, and parent factor **often** affect the students' competence. The teacher's personality, and teaching strategy, facilities and equipment **always** influence the mastery of students' competencies in food processing.

Furthermore, it shows that reviewing their lessons, preparing for pre-test and post-test, spending vacant time doing assignments or studying their lessons and finishing their studies and homework before using internet **sometimes** affect their competence, same through with their teacher's use of power point to deliver her lesson.

This means that food-processing students tend not to have good study habits which could affect their competencies and their performance in school. Ponnuraj (2023) mentions that lack of good study habits is the issue that most students experience, which adds to their bad performance on tests and exams. A student needs to develop strong study habits to achieve well. Study habit is an action that students routinely and habitually carry out to complete the task of learning, including reading, taking notes, and holding study sessions. Depending on how well they benefit the learner, study habits can either be deemed effective or ineffective. Study habits aid students in understanding their coursework and in creating a comfortable and engaging learning environment.

Table 11
Factors Affecting the Competencies of the Students in Agriculture

I. Student Related Factors	Mean	Qualitative Description
A. Interest		
1. I prepare myself for the specialization subject.	4.36	Always
2. I actively participate during the discussion by answering self-check.	4.28	Always
3. I listen attentively to the lecture of my specialization teacher.	4.44	Always
4. I classify things/lessons I do not understand.	4.00	Often
5. I perform the task given by the teacher by following the standard specification	4.28	Always
Total Mean	4.27	Always
B. Study Habits		
1. I review my lesson and prepare for pre-test and post-test.	4.17	Often

2. I spend my free time doing assignments or studying my lessons.	4.08	Often
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B. Study Habits	Mean	Qualitative Description
3. I prefer finishing my study and homework first before using the internet/watching TV.	4.06	Often
4. I exert more effort when my teacher gives me a performance task.	4.61	Always
5. I study harder to improve my performance when I get few performance grades.	4.69	Always
Total Mean	4.32	Always
II. Teachers – Related Factors		
A. Teaching Personality		
1. My teacher is student friendly.	4.50	Always
2. My teacher has appealing personality with good sense of humor.	4.61	Always
3. My teacher is smart and fair in making decisions.	4.64	Always
4. My teacher always gives praise.	4.61	Always
5. My teacher is open to suggestions and opinions.	4.69	Always
Total Mean	4.61	Always
B. Teaching Strategy		
1. My teacher explains the objectives of the lesson clearly at the very beginning.	4.72	Always
2. My teacher has mastery of the subject matter	4.56	Always
3. My teacher is a National Certificate and Trainers Methodology holder.	4.61	Always
4. My teacher is updated with present competencies needed.	4.69	Always
5. My teacher uses various strategies and techniques in presenting the lessons.	4.72	Always
Total Mean	4.66	Always
C. Instructional Materials		
1. My teacher uses power point presentation to deliver his/her lesson.	4.64	Always

2. My teacher uses local materials to execute the performance task.	4.64	Always
Total Mean	4.64	Always

D. Facilities and Equipment	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Learning facilities provided (library, specialization laboratory, computer laboratory & checkboard) are used by students.	4.44	Always
2. Learning facilities in performing the task in their field of specialization are used.	4.58	Always
3. The specialization laboratory of the lecture area is standard and washable (classroom size, lighting, air conditioning, table & chair)	2.53	Rarely
Total Mean	3.85	Often
III. Administrative Support Factor		
1. Address issues promptly and effectively	4.37	Always
2. Accepts responsibility to facilitate programs	4.53	Always
3. Fairly allocates funding support programs	4.53	Always
4. Effectively support students generating projects	4.42	Always
5. Effectively supports and facilitates students advising and progress	5.00	Always
6. Facilitates student activities to enhance development	4.74	Always
Total Mean	4.60	Always
IV. Parent Factor		
1. Parents provide all their materials needed to perform well in their field of specialization.	4.58	Always
2. Has adequate parental support	4.33	Always
3. Consistently monitor their children's progress	4.47	Always
4. Check outputs of their children	4.44	Always
5. Motivates their children in times of overlapping activities	4.44	Always
Total Mean	4.45	Always
WAM	4.44	Always

Table 11 presents the factors affecting the competencies of Agriculture students. It shows that three factors **always** affect their competencies- the student factors, the teacher-related factors, and the administrative factors. The facilities and equipment **often** affect students' competencies. Overall, the student, teacher, administrative, and parent factors **always** affect the competencies of the organic agriculture students.

The data further shows that the laboratory and lecture area is standard and washable (classroom size, lighting, air conditioning, table, and chair). This means that the competency of students is affected by their physical learning environment. It has been said that in technical-vocational schools, facilities and equipment are important.

This is supported by the study of Alferez and Palmes (2024) which found that both administrators and teacher respondents were assessed as very satisfactory on items of Competency Assessment and Certification, Instructional and Teacher Support Material, Curriculum Instruction, Program and Project Management, and Monitoring and Evaluation. On the one hand, both respondents registered only as satisfactory on the aspect of facilities and services. This can be because budgetary allocation in this area is insufficient.

In summary, the competencies of the TVL Students with specialization in aquaculture and organic agriculture are **always** affected by factors like the student himself, the teachers, the administration and the parents. The carpentry and food processing students, on the other hand, are often affected by these factors.

The findings further show that the food processing and carpentry students are not motivated and need support from their parents. When asked, the students disclosed that they are not motivated to go to school because their parents most of the time do not give them support. Parents do not mind if they need something in school, especially the materials they need to comply to pass the competencies. They also added that they do not even attend parent meetings for them to be aware of what will happen regarding immersion.

The study of Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) that to comply with the system of integrated support for their students, schools need to build a partnership with parents and develop mutual responsibility for students' success in the educational system. In this way, parental involvement is increased, parents' efforts to support schools are encouraged, and they are directly making a positive impact on a successful educational system. Parental involvement can encourage children's and adolescents' achievement in many ways. One way that parents can contribute positively to their children's education is to assist them with their academic work at home. Parents who read to their children, assist them with their homework, and provide tutoring using resources provided by teachers tend to do better in school than children whose parents do not assist them. Furthermore, research shows that the level of parental involvement is associated with academic success. Students excel even more when their parents assist them at home with their homework, attend school-sponsored events, and volunteer at their children's schools.

3. Is there a significant difference in the factors affecting the competencies of students when grouped according to specialization?

a. Student Related Factors

Table 12
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Effect of Student-Related Factors On the Level of Competence of the Senior High School Students When Grouped According to Specialization

Student Related Factors	Mean				P-value of F	Analysis	Remarks
	Aquaculture	Carpentry	Food Processing	Organic Agriculture Production			
Interest	4.53	4.12	3.71	4.44	7.6294 E-8	P < 0.05	Significant
Study Habits	4.41	3.61	3.45	4.22	4.0583 E - 10	P < 0.05	Significant

The results of the tests of significant difference in the effect of student-related factors on the level of competencies of the SHS when grouped according to specialization are presented in Table 12.

It is evident from the results that the P- P-values of F are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the student related factors affecting the level of competence of the SHS when grouped according to specialization. It shows that the students' interest and study habits significantly differ in their effect on students specializing in aquaculture, organic agriculture, carpentry, and food processing. It further implies that the students' interest and study habits have more effect on the competence of students specializing in Aquaculture compared to the rest of the students.

In essence, while there may be some common factors influencing all students, the specific ways in which they perceive and approach these factors can be significantly influenced by their specialization.

b. Teacher- Related Factor

Table 13
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Effect of Teacher-Related Factors on the Level of Competence of the Senior High School Students When Grouped According to Specialization

m	Mean				P-value of F	Analysis	Remarks
	Aquaculture	Carpentry	Food Processing	Organic Agriculture Production			
Teaching Personality	4.49	4.31	4.18	4.69	0.0132	P < 0.05	Significant
Teaching Strategy	4.60	4.41	4.32	4.77	0.0356	P < 0.05	Significant
Instructional Materials	4.18	3.97	3.97	4.65	1.5259 E-7	P < 0.05	Significant

Table 13 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the effect of teacher-related factors on the level of competence of the SHS when grouped according to specialization.

The results reveal that the F probability values are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is a significant difference in the teacher-related factors affecting the level of competence of the SHS when grouped according to specialization. It shows that the teacher-related factors, like teaching personality, teaching strategy, and instructional materials, have different levels of effect on the students' level of competence. As evidenced by the mean values, the three areas of teacher-related factors have a stronger effect on the students taking Organic Agriculture Production than on the rest of the students.

Studies suggest that hands-on learning and exposure to real-world farming practices, common in organic agriculture, can foster a positive and more holistic learning experience, potentially influencing students' perceptions of their teachers. A study made by Iyagba and Ekpete (2017) show that organic farming can be done within a school environment. A greater percentage (85.9%) of the teachers agreed to practice Organic Farming (OF), the most planted crop in the schools is cassava (38.8%), majorly practiced intercropping and 31.2% of the respondents were unwilling to inform their co-teachers of the benefits of. The respondents also accepted the need for elaborate knowledge and in-service training on OF, an inadequate Agricultural Science curriculum to teach OF, as well as better facilities and teaching methods.

c. Administrative Support Factor, Parent Factor, Facilities and Equipment

Table 14
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Effect of Administrative Factor, Parent Factor, and Facilities and Equipment On The Level of Competence of the Senior High School Students When Grouped According to Specialization

Factors	Mean				P-value of F	Analysis	Remarks
	Aquaculture	Carpentry	Food Processing	Organic Agriculture Production			
Administrative Support	4.55	3.83	3.86	4.66	3.0518 E-7	P < 0.05	Significant
Parent Factor	4.37	4.14	3.67	4.62	1.5300 E-7	P < 0.05	Significant
Facilities and Equipment	4.35	4.06	4.05	4.58	0.0198	P < 0.05	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the effect of administrative support, parent, and facilities and equipment factors affecting the level of competence of SHS when grouped according to specialization are disclosed in Table 14.

It is evident from the results that the P- P-values of F are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the effect of administrative support, parent and facilities and equipment on the level of competence of SHS when grouped according to specialization. It implies that these factors affect more the students in Organic Agriculture Production as indicated by the mean values in the table.

The students in organic agriculture production receive administrative and parental support through some training given to the coastal towns. Accordingly, the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) Provincial Science and Technology Center (DOST-PSTC Isabela (2024) in partnership with the National Irrigation Administration- Isabela Irrigation Management Office (NIA-Isabela IMO), recently trained farmers of Barangay Dibulo, Dinapigue, Isabela on “Organic Fertilizer and Production of Natural Farm Inputs.” These initiatives support the Organic Agriculture Act 10068, an act providing for the development and promotion of organic agriculture in the Philippines and other purposes. The training was very appropriate for Dinapigue since farming is one of its main economic activities that provides livelihood opportunities for the farmers and their families. Dinapigue is the southernmost coastal town of the province of Isabela and is one of the four remote and isolated coastal towns facing the Philippine Sea in the east, and is separated from the rest of the province by the Sierra Madre Mountains.

4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of competence of SHS and the identified factors?

Table 15
Result of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Level of Competence of Senior High School Students and the Identified Factors

Level of Competence of SHS and the following Identified Factors	P-value of r	Analysis	Remarks
1. Student Related Factor			
a. interest	1.25 E- 4	P < 0.05	Significant
b. Study Habits	6.25 E- 5	P < 0.05	Significant
2. Teachers Related Factors			
a. Teaching Personality	0.0309	P < 0.05	Significant
b. Teaching Strategy	0.0010	P < 0.05	Significant
c. Instructional Materials	2.5 E- 4	P < 0.05	Significant
3. Administrative Support Factor	0.0005	P < 0.05	Significant
4. Parent Factor	0.0263	P < 0.05	Significant
5. Facilities and Equipment	0.0156	P < 0.05	Significant

Table 15 displays the results of the test of the significant relationship between the level of competence of SHS students and the identified factors.

The results show that the P-values of r are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the level of competence of SHS students and the identified factors. It implies that the students' interest and study habits, the teachers' teaching personality and strategy, instructional materials, the administrative and parental support, and the facilities and equipment significantly affect the students' level of competence.

In the study of Curan (2023), he found that despite having weak interests, students were still interested in learning various subcomponents of various skills in TLE. Salient findings yielded that learners are more interested in learning about TLE competencies despite their perceptions of it being difficult. They are more likely to be interested when they believe they are good at the subject, have the knowledge, and can succeed despite the practical works involved in the TLE subject. They are more likely to be interested in learning its competencies when they enjoy activities, love their practicum, are motivated internally, and prefer TLE over other subjects. Students are more interested in learning competencies when teachers possess adequate materials and the necessary competencies to teach the subject. Curan recommended that stakeholders in the education industry should design a curriculum with specific specialization for incoming Grade 9 learners, providing facilities and equipment for practical works, while being considerate of their interests. Conducting surveys to identify the best TLE specialized courses can increase interest and sustain it. The importance of TLE in students' lives must be emphasized by educators by teaching practical competencies in Home

Economics, Agri-fishery Arts, Industrial Arts, and Information and Communication Technology.

Conclusions

Students in the schools in the coastal towns, especially in Palanan, have different levels of competence in the TVE basic, common, and core competencies as assessed by the students themselves and their teachers. Students specializing in Agriculture and Aquaculture met all the competencies, while those in Food Processing and Carpentry met some competencies.

The level of competence of students in their respective specialization is affected by several factors, particularly students' interest and study habits; teachers' personality and teaching strategies; instructional materials, facilities and equipment; and administrative and parental support.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Since the teacher factor highly affects the students' mastery of the competencies, the Department of Education (DepEd) should give priority to teacher training and seminars to enhance strategies in teaching TVL skills. Also, materials needed for the TVL track should be given to the proper hands-on activities of students.
2. The Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) should strengthen the partnership and working collaboration with the DepEd to promote skills development programs.
3. Curriculum Planners should address the emerging demand for a relevant and responsive curriculum, which will enhance the designed curriculum and make it more appropriate to fit the needs of the TVL students.
4. School Heads are encouraged to create comprehensive plans to address the situation and needs of the learners and become competent in their own field of specialization.
5. Since teaching strategies affect the mastery of competencies by the students, Teachers should adopt appropriate methodologies and effective guidance that would greatly improve and increase the percentage rate of assessment readiness of the students.
6. The results of the study should be shared with students and teachers to offer insights for improving their performance in their area of specialization and to motivate them to be competent in the National Assessment.

7. Parents should strongly support their children, especially in providing the materials needed in their chosen specialization.
8. Future Researchers can conduct studies related to how students can increase their performance in their field of specialization in Technical Vocational Education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards to ensure the protection of the rights and welfare of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, including Senior High School students and their teachers, after they were fully briefed on the study's purpose, procedures, and their roles in it. Participation was voluntary, and participants were assured that they could withdraw from the study at any time without facing negative consequences. The confidentiality of participant responses was maintained, and no personal identifiers were used in reporting the results. Data was securely stored, with access limited to authorized personnel only. The study was designed to minimize any physical, psychological, or emotional harm, ensuring that no discomfort was caused to participants. Participants were treated with respect and their views and opinions were valued, without any form of discrimination or bias. Ethical approval was granted by the Schools Division Superintendent of Isabela, and the researcher ensured compliance with the institution's ethical guidelines. Furthermore, the study was conducted with integrity, ensuring that data collection was accurate and that the findings were presented in an unbiased manner, contributing to the academic community and supporting improvements in the Strengthened Technical-Vocational Education Program.

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